

Humic Acids from Himalayan Lake Sediments. Stability Constants with Copper and Zinc

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IN recent years heavy metal pollution has been reported from various parts of the world¹. The humic acids being negatively charged polyelectrolytes normally complex with positively charged metal ions. Some reports are available in the literature on the stability constants of metal ions with humic acids²⁻⁴ using different techniques. In the present investigation an attempt has been made to study metal-humic acid complex formation (copper and zinc) with humic acids from diverse

as the intercept and slope of the plot of $(2-\bar{n})a^2/\bar{n}$ against $(1-\bar{n})a/\bar{n}$, where a is the ligand concentration.

Results and Discussion

The titration curves of humic acids exhibited partial sigmoidal character, and also their protonation constants were within the same range. Total titratable functional groups, base-exchange capacities and humification values of humic acids have been presented in Table 1. The humic acids of Anchar lake exhibited protonation constant at relatively higher pH during the titration.

The formation curves for the copper-humic acid systems are given in Fig. 1. The experimental values are in good agreement with that reported^{5,6}. It is obvious from Table 2 that the stability constants of copper-humic acid complexes ranged from 6.4×10^5 to 2.1×10^7 (β_1), and 1.39×10^7 to 4.5×10^{10} (β_2). The copper-humic acid complex of Mansbal lake (M_s) showed highest stability, β_1 in this case being approximately thousand times higher than the other humic acid samples which were of the

TABLE 1—HUMIFICATION, TITRATABLE FUNCTIONAL GROUPS (T_{ClO}) AND PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF HUMIC ACIDS

Lake/site	Trophic status	Depth m	$\Delta \log K$	Base exchange capacity meq/100 g	$T_{ClO} \times 10^{-4}$	pK_1
Dal lake (D _s)	Eutrophic	2.5	0.887	80	1.24	4.80
Wular lake (W _s)	Mesotrophic	8.7	0.523	40	4.20	4.52
Mansbal lake (M _s)	Eutrophic	1.7	0.259	80	2.32	4.75
(M _s)	Mesotrophic	12.0	0.438	80	2.24	4.49
Anchar lake (A _s)	Eutrophic	8.0	0.812	40	1.52	6.20

lake environments (Table 1). From an environmental point of view, complexing of metal ions by humic acids is of importance in determining the fate of these pollutants in the eco-system.

Experimental

The humic acids were extracted according to the reported method⁵, and were purified by prolonged dialysis against distilled water. pH measurements were carried out on a ECL 5651 digital pH meter at 25°. Nitrogen was bubbled during the course of titration, through the titration cell. Humic acid solutions were prepared by dissolving humic acid (1 g) in 0.02 N KOH (500 ml). 1 N KNO₃ was used to maintain the ionic strength at 0.2 M. All the functions like $\bar{n}H$ and $\bar{n}$ were calculated by Bjerrum-Calvin titration technique⁶. On the basis of $\bar{n}$ and pH data the stability constants of metal-humic acid complexes were calculated by graphical method⁷. The $1/\beta_2$ and β_1/β_2 values were obtained

Fig. 1. Formation curve for the copper-humic acid systems: (●) A_s, (Δ) D_s, and (□) W_s.

same order of magnitude. β_2 was also higher for Mansbal lake (M_s) sample. It is interesting to note that stability constants followed inversely the degree of humification ($\Delta \log K$ value), as M_s showed low humification (exhibiting high $\Delta \log K$ value). This is in agreement with Matsuda and Ito⁸, who observed an increase in the stability constants of complexes of humic acids with metal ions such as copper, zinc and lead. It was further observed in our experiment that the stability constants of zinc-humic acid (M_s) complexes were almost equal to that of copper-humic acid complexes ($\beta_1 = 2.0 \times 10^7$ and $\beta_2 = 4.3 \times 10^{10}$), although the two metal ions differ significantly in their reactivity.

TABLE 2—STABILITY OF COPPER-HUMIC ACID COMPLEXES

Site	β_1	β_2
M_s	2.1×10^7	4.5×10^{10}
A_s	13.1×10^8	4.31×10^7
W_s	16.6×10^8	7.06×10^7
D_s	15.8×10^8	1.4×10^8

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References

1. R. COENEN, R. FEHRENBACH, W. FRITSCH, S. GORTZMAN, H. D. PIOTROWSKI and R. SCHLADITZ, *Naturwissenschaften*, 1972, 59, 106.
2. O. K. BORGAARD, *Acta Chem. Scand., Ser. A*, 1974, 121.
3. F. J. STEVENSON, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am.*, 1976, 40, 665.
4. T. TAKAMATSU and T. YOSHIDA, *Soil Sci.*, 1978, 125, 977.
5. M. V. M. DESAI and A. K. GANGULY, Report No. 422, BARC, Bombay, 1970.
6. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solutions", Hæse and Sons, Copenhagen, 1941.
7. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
8. K. MATSUDA and S. IIO, *Soil Sci. Plant Nutr. (Tokyo)*, 1970, 16, 1.

Use of Molybdate. Oxidative Decarboxylation of α -Hydroxycarboxylic Acids

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UNLIKE Cr^{VI} compounds, the application of Mo and W as oxidising agents in their higher valency states is very rare in synthetic organic chemistry

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though they belong to the same group of transition elements. It was observed that ammonium molybdate in boiling hydrochloric acid (6N) could convert arylmethanols into the corresponding aromatic aldehydes in good yield¹. This unique oxidation never went beyond the aldehyde stage. In the course of our investigation to explore the scope of this reagent, it was observed that under specific condition this reagent can effect oxidative decarboxylation of certain α -hydroxycarboxylic acids (1) to the respective carbonyl compounds (2).

The oxidations of alcohols using Mo^{VI} complexes², allylic alcohols by molybdenum catalysed *t*-butylhydroperoxide³ and various types of organic compounds employing hydrogen peroxide with molybdate as catalyst⁴⁻⁶ have been reported, and the present investigation describes another new application of Mo^{VI} as an oxidant. Ammonium (or sodium) molybdate is a stable, non-toxic and readily available reagent which may be chosen only with those cases where there is no undesirable side-reaction for boiling the substrate in 6N hydrochloric acid.

Benzilic acid (1; X=Y=C₆H₅) was selected as the pilot compound to establish the optimum condition for the oxidation to yield the desired benzophenone (2; X=Y=C₆H₅). Thus a mixture of benzilic acid (0.5 g) and ammonium molybdate (2.5 g) were refluxed in 6N hydrochloric acid (15 ml) and dimethyl sulphoxide (5 ml) for 4 h. On usual work-up benzophenone was obtained in almost quantitative yield. Replacement of dimethyl sulphoxide by either glacial acetic acid or dimethyl formamide did not affect the yield of the product but the work-up of the reaction mixture was very difficult due to the formation of emulsion. The effect of variation of the refluxing time, reaction temperature and quantity of ammonium molybdate used has also been studied. The variation of the amount of ammonium molybdate revealed that the use of equimolar quantities of the reagent and the substrates was essential for a good yield of the product. It was observed that 2.3 g (0.01 mol) of benzilic acid required 12 g (0.01 mol) of ammonium molybdate and heating under reflux for 4 h with 6N hydrochloric acid was the ideal condition for this oxidation. Similarly, 9-carboxy-9-hydroxyfluorene was oxidised to furnish fluorenone in quantitative yield. Mandelic acid required almost double the quantity of the oxidant and gave a mixture of benzaldehyde (10%), benzoyl formic acid (60%) and benzoic acid (20%). Other aliphatic α -hydroxy acids like citric, tartaric and glycollic under similar optimum condition furnished the desired oxidation products in only 10–15% yield. It appears that the yield of the desired product would be excellent with aromatic substrates but quite low with aliphatic compounds because of the